

INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP – A FACTOR FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT: *The development of innovative entrepreneurship plays an indispensable role in achieving economic success and high rates of economic growth. Thus, entrepreneurship as an economic entity and a special creative type of economic behaviour is an integral part of the many factors for achieving economic success. Innovative activity in the modern economy is becoming a defining feature of entrepreneurship. Innovation is not simply an invention or discovery, but also includes the practical application of an entrepreneurial idea, i.e., the commercialisation of new technical, technological, organisational and other developments. Entrepreneurship is widely recognised as a driver of economic growth and is seen by many as a solution to contemporary economic and social problems, as well as an opportunity to promote environmental and economic sustainability. The paper aims to deepen knowledge about innovation, its role in the modern economy, and to present the link between innovation and sustainable development. The study uses an integrated methodological approach, including analysis of statistical data and review of scientific literature.*

KEYWORDS: *innovative entrepreneurship; sustainable innovations; sustainable development; innovations; economic growth*

JEL CODES: *L26, O1, O31, O40*

Introduction

In today's world of globalisation and scientific and technological explosion, innovation has become a key driver for ensuring successful competitiveness and sustainable development. Analysts and visionaries point out that modern civilisation is on the verge of significant changes – a transition from the industrial to the post-industrial or information stage.

The accelerated development of science and technology and easier access to human achievements are causing dynamic changes in the socio-economic environment. It is necessary to rethink the role and importance of innovation, the implementation of which leads to a complete change in our daily lives, rethinking the conditions for building and developing an internal innovation system that stimulates demand for innovative products and technologies, as well as developing the necessary infrastructure and system for data collection and analysis. Analyzing strategic guidelines, possible risks, and solutions helps accelerate the innovation process, increase the effectiveness of the implementation of scientific and technical achievements, and ensure the sustainability of economic development and social prosperity.

The impact of innovation on sustainable development is indisputable. In fact, they are inextricably linked and mutually dependent (Ivanova, 2018). Innovation makes a huge contribution to the formation of the material basis of prosperity, while sustainable development requires uniformity in the process of change, with strict coordination of the direction of scientific and technological development, investment, and institutional policy.

In recent years, research has increasingly focused on the link between innovation and sustainable development. According to various experts, sustainable development cannot be discussed without taking into account innovation and its long-term effects. Innovation should not be limited to the renewal of products/services and markets, because that is not enough. Innovation must be applied to technological processes, working methods, working relationships, and the relationships of organisations with the outside world, especially

stakeholders, financiers, suppliers and, last but not least, their customers (Scărlătescu, 2020).

Contemporary economic development is unthinkable without innovation. Scientific and technical flexibility determines the high innovative potential of the economy in implementing new ideas, allowing it to respond to market demands and perform effectively in a dynamic competitive environment. However, in recent years, increasing attention has been paid to the impact of innovative economic activities on the environment. The focus is on the responsible management of natural resources – a significant factor for sustainable development.

The article aims to deepen knowledge about innovations, their role in the modern economy, and the relationship between innovation and sustainable development, with sustainability being viewed as the ability to maintain or support economic, environmental, or social processes over time without depleting natural resources (Mollenkamp, 2025). It also includes an assessment of existing issues and barriers, an analysis of the effectiveness of government programs to support science and innovation, and an evaluation of measures aimed at creating favourable conditions for sustainable development, improving the quality of education, and stimulating the development of innovative infrastructure.

The study uses an integrated methodological approach, including statistical data analysis and scientific literature review. The methods used include both quantitative and qualitative data analysis. Official statistical data, reports from government agencies and international institutions, and scientific publications are included, which made it possible to analyse the state and prospects of sustainable innovation and entrepreneurship, identify the main problems, and develop recommendations for improving the conditions for stimulating innovative entrepreneurship.

Innovative entrepreneurship and sustainable development

The term *innovation* has Latin origins and means novelty, but its introduction into economic theory and practice and its transformation into an independent subject of scientific research is thanks to the Austrian economist Joseph Schumpeter, who formulated in his work "*The Theory of Economic Development*" (1911) a scientific approach that focuses on innovation as a productive function that influences qualitative changes in production factors and the production process itself. "Initially, J. Schumpeter examined the innovation process within the framework of medium-term dynamics, which means, above all, investment in the development and creation of new products" (Scherbakov, 2019). According to the Austrian researcher's economic theory, economic development is due precisely to innovation. Thus, Schumpeter established himself as a pioneer in perceiving innovation as the foundation for economic development.

There are various definitions of innovation in economic literature, but the numerous interpretations by authors are not the subject of this study. However, according to the international reference manual for collecting and using data on innovation, the Oslo Manuel (2005), innovation is the introduction of a new or significantly improved product (good or service) or process, a new marketing method, or a new organisational method in business practices, workplace organisation, or external relations. The main thesis of this manual is that innovation can and should be measured, which makes it possible to determine the scale of innovation activities, the characteristics of innovative companies, and the internal and systemic factors that can influence innovation.

In order to assess innovative entrepreneurship and its role in sustainable development, indicators are needed to measure the level of innovation. In general, innovation in enterprises is assessed by taking into account the increase in the volume of new products manufactured and sold, the increase in the share of high-tech exports, the

number of patents applied for and registered, and the degree to which specific objectives have been achieved. The ability of enterprises to develop through renewal is measured by the level and increase in the intensity of research and development (R&D) activity, i.e. by the ratio between R&D expenditure and the volume of annual production of enterprises (Chobanova, 2023).

On the other hand, sustainability, in the broadest sense, refers to the ability to maintain or support a process continuously over time. In a business and political context, sustainability aims to prevent the depletion of natural or physical resources so that they remain available in the long term (Mollenkamp, 2025). This means that sustainable development also shapes the social framework that determines public welfare and requires an integrated approach that reflects the innovative nature of the present, the mitigation of environmental problems, and dynamic economic development.

Initially, the concept of sustainable development seems alien to the economic world until it integrates the social and environmental impacts of individual economic activities. The concept was developed outside the economic framework, even in opposition to capitalism, embodied in the works of leading liberal economists, who initially refrained from and refused any participation and even transferred these public responsibilities to state agencies (Geddardudrov, 2015). But in 1987, the concept was expressed in the Brundtland Report, named after the chair of the UN Commission on Environment and Development, Ms. Gro Harlem Brundtland, and entitled "*Our Common Future*." This document became the leading concept for sustainable development and stated that the most serious environmental problems on a global scale were mainly due to the extreme poverty prevailing in the South and the unsustainable patterns of consumption and production practiced in the North. It defines sustainable development as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (Le Rapport Brundtland, 1987).

In September 2015, the member states of the UN General Assembly signed the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and adopted its 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), covering social, environmental, and economic aspects. The economic aspects include building sustainable infrastructure, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and encouraging innovation; ensuring sustainable consumption and production patterns; strengthening the means of implementation and revitalising the global partnership for sustainable development (The 17 Goals, 2015). All of the goals outlined in the document are important for sustainable development and challenge countries to commit to directing policy towards international cooperation in the field of sustainable development and its economic, social, environmental, and governance dimensions.

In its efforts to build a better and more sustainable world, the UN finds a natural partner in the European Union. The EU sees the values expressed in the SDGs as a useful framework for designing and implementing international partnerships, and through its external action, the Union plays a leading role in the implementation of the UN Agenda 2030 on a global scale. However, despite the efforts of the UN and the EU, sustainable development and innovation policy have not yet been accepted globally as interlinked drivers of public welfare. Unfortunately, UN and EU policies are often interpreted and perceived at corporate level as regulatory constraints that hinder production profitability and market competition.

In recent years, patterns of entrepreneurship and consumption have undergone significant shifts, leading to social and environmental changes. There is ongoing debate about the significant growth of production activities, the overexploitation of natural resources, and the effects on environmental protection and conservation. Organisations thus face new requirements and constraints, and their competitiveness now also depends on the

adoption and effective implementation of sustainability-oriented innovation management (Scărlătescu, 2020).

Sustainability is the ability to develop in a relatively stable and continuous way, and it also includes understanding sustainable innovation, which is defined as developing and implementing new products, services, technologies, or business models that have a positive environmental, social, and economic impact. The goal of sustainable innovation is to meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Jain, 2022).

Figure 1. Sustainable development

Source: Jain Nick. What is Sustainable Innovation? Definition, Examples and Best Practices. 2022, <https://ideascale.com/blog/sustainable-innovation/>

The development and implementation of sustainable innovations (Figure 1) aims to minimise the consumption of fossil fuels, reduce pollution and promote the use of renewable sources, thereby mitigating climate change. Added to this is the social impact—addressing challenges such as poverty, access to education, quality healthcare, and others, i.e., creating and developing products or services that improve people's quality of life without jeopardising the current generation or future generations.

Without a doubt, sustainable innovation not only does not ignore economic prosperity, but also helps generate economic benefits and ensure long-term profitability. Businesses engaged in sustainable innovation develop new business models and strategies, adhering to consumer demands and taking into account requirements for fair working conditions, environmentally friendly processes and products, and more.

Both traditional and sustainable innovations involve the development of new products, services, or processes and can lead to revolutionary changes. They are interrelated, but there are also differences between them, with the key differences lying in their focus, purpose, and approach. Sustainable innovation focuses on overcoming environmental, social, and economic challenges by developing and implementing solutions. Their goal is to create products and services whose impact will ensure the well-being of current and future generations, and their approach is based mainly on existing technologies and practices, seeking to develop and apply them in such a way as to reduce negative impacts and increase positive outcomes. However, sustainable innovations can lead to revolutionary changes by rejecting existing practices, technologies, and business models in order to create more sustainable alternative options.

The concept of sustainable innovation is complex, interdisciplinary, and requires joint action. Companies must open up to other sectors of activity in order to unlock the value of sustainable innovation. This transforms the company's "value chain" into a "value network" (eCampusOntario, 2023). Partnerships between different stakeholders-business,

government institutions, research centers, non-governmental organisations, regional communities – is a prerequisite for the development of sustainable innovation, because only by combining efforts, knowledge and resources can greater success and sustainable solutions to the challenges that arise be achieved.

Innovative entrepreneurship is the entrepreneurship of the future, but it must be consistent with the idea of sustainability and sustainable innovation. In this regard, the concept introduced in 1994 by John Elkington, called "Triple Bottom Line" (TBL), deserves attention. According to this concept, business is built on the "three pillars of sustainable development" – the planet, people, and profit (Elkington). Although the use of TBL as a management tool faces a number of difficulties in identifying and quantifying innovation potential and combining it with social aspects, this concept outlines the need to focus on more sustainable technologies, entrepreneurial models, and industries.

Contemporary entrepreneurship, whose defining characteristic is innovative activity, i.e., the practical implementation of innovations to implement entrepreneurial ideas and commercialise new technical, technological, organisational and other developments, depends both on the level of technological and economic development of the national economy, on the ability of society to take advantage of technological innovations, and on the opportunities for implementing sustainable innovations, whose main dimensions are environmental, social and economic. Innovative sustainable entrepreneurship is risky entrepreneurship associated with costs for scientific research, project work, and pilot production. The process involves searching for a new idea and assessing its sustainability, preparing a business plan, seeking the necessary resources, implementing the innovative product and its commercialisation, proactive management, which requires careful planning and communication with all stakeholders – from employees to customers, investors, and partners (Brian, 2022), as well as government institutions and non-governmental organisations, in pursuit of a common goal. Based on the above, we can propose the following measures for the development and stimulation of innovative entrepreneurship, which must be taken:

- Active implementation of state policy for the establishment and development of national innovation systems. The development, maintenance, and adequate updating of national innovation systems requires increased feedback between the economy and science, which justifies the scientific race and the struggle for human capital, and determines the place of each national economy in the global economy. The systematisation of the main theses of contemporary innovation theory is a topical issue with a view to solving not only theoretical but also practical problems.
- Improving the legal framework – from intellectual property protection to improving the legal basis for an innovative economy and sustainable development. This requires the application of a systematic approach to the management of innovation processes at the national level, integrating a variety of scientific methods that allow the unification of multiple processes and organisations to achieve comprehensive results. Unfortunately, Bulgaria does not even perform satisfactorily in this area. The Bulgarian Industrial Association's analysis, based on data from the *Global Innovation Index*, shows a decline in the "Institutions" pillar, with our country dropping 17 positions to 83rd place in 2024. Our position is no better in terms of the effectiveness of our institutions. Bulgaria performs worse than countries such as Ghana, Tanzania, Kazakhstan, Serbia, and North Macedonia (**Bulgarian Industrial Association, 2024**).
- Stimulating fundamental and applied science, recognising that support for scientific potential plays an important role in the sustainable development of any country. It is necessary to increase funding for research and development, investment in the

development of innovative technologies and industries, and to provide scientific knowledge and highly qualified personnel with a vision for sustainable development.

- Supporting innovative entrepreneurship, which plays a key role in achieving sustainable development and transforming the economy into an innovative and socially oriented model. It is clear that an innovative focus in the economy will be the main link in ensuring the country's sustainable development, and the innovative activity of enterprises will accompany the creation of favourable conditions for the development of innovative activity, for strengthening economic security and sustainable development.

- Development of human capital, a key factor in the transition of the country's economy to an innovative and sustainable path of development, enabling it to dramatically increase its competitiveness by enhancing its comparative advantages in science, education, and high technology.

All this points to the need to build a solid institutional infrastructure, primarily aimed at creating conditions for the unimpeded dissemination of knowledge and information among participants in the information process, linking not only organisations directly involved in the innovation process, but also organisations that create conditions for its successful implementation or provide a market for innovative products (Ivanova, 2018).

Statistics on innovative entrepreneurship in Europe reflect the dynamics of the EU economy through the adaptation of economic structures to changing market conditions and the strengthening of competitiveness. The potential contribution that this type of enterprise can make is an important aspect that is the focus of attention for policymakers worldwide and highlights the impact of innovation on revenue generation and sustainability.

According to data from the Global Innovation Index for 2023, there is a trend of improvement in the overall scores of all countries in the top 40, with the exception of Bulgaria (-0.5) and Malta (-0.1). Switzerland tops the ranking for the 13th consecutive year, leading in the categories "Knowledge and Technology Outputs" and "Creative Outputs." Sweden returns to second place, ranking first in the categories: *business sophistication, and researchers*. The US ranks third in the ranking but remains the economy that leads in the largest number of indicators (13/80), some of which are corporate investment in R&D, value of venture capital investment received, quality of higher education, value of unicorns, software expenditure, and value of corporate intangible assets intensity (Figure 2). (**Bulgarian Industrial Association, 2023**)

Figure 2. Global Innovation Index 2023

Source: **Bulgarian Industrial Association.** <https://www.bia-bg.com/analyses/view/32504/>

Between 2013 and 2023, the intensity of R&D in the EU increased by 0.1 percentage points (pp), according to Eurostat data. During this period, R&D intensity increased in 19 EU countries, with the largest increases recorded in Belgium (1.0 percentage points), Poland (0.7 percentage points), and Greece (0.7 percentage points). In contrast, five EU countries reported R&D intensity below 1%: Romania (0.5%), Malta (0.6%), Cyprus (0.7%), Bulgaria and Latvia (both 0.8%). Bulgaria is also among the lowest in terms of growth in expenditure relative to GDP – 0.16 pp between 2013 and 2023. (Economic Life, 2024). Prof. Chobanova even points out that Bulgaria has not achieved economic development with increasing R&D intensity. After the drastic decline at the beginning of the transition, it has remained at around 0.5% for more than 20 years, which is six times lower than the Lisbon target and three times lower than the national target (Chobanova, 2023, p. 479).

In addition, it has been established that with Bulgaria's accession to the EU, businesses have significantly increased their share of national R&D expenditure, but this is not related to their performance. The lack of sufficient demand for new products and services, as well as for intellectual property produced in Bulgaria, renders Bulgarian companies unable to innovate in the face of global competition. Not only will they lag behind other EU countries in terms of increasing their innovation intensity, but the number of innovative enterprises will also decline despite the growth in the number of SMEs. (Chobanova, 2023, p. 480).

Innovation is becoming increasingly important in the era of transition of national economies to the modern technological era, and on a global scale, the following innovation policies can be identified as the basis for sustainable economic growth: growth in innovation funding and an increase in the volume of knowledge-intensive products manufactured; growing importance of revolutionary innovations, with Germany leading the way in the application of revolutionary innovations; development of transnational cooperation in the field of innovation; diversification of sources of innovation funding, with the business environment being the leading source of innovation funding in developed countries; an increase in the share of developing countries in global innovation production and innovation funding (Krasova E.V., Chen Yanchun, 2017).

Combining the concept of sustainable development with the creation, dissemination, and implementation of innovations in various spheres of human activity contributes not only to increasing the efficiency of national economies and their competitiveness, but also to achieving social, ethical and environmental goals aimed at balancing social upheavals and minimising the losses that may arise in society and nature.

To achieve these goals, it is essential to introduce new management techniques designed to accomplish the tasks related to sustainable development. The change must begin within the organisation, with institutional support, by developing a model of sustainable management innovation that prioritises long-term planning, fair distribution, and stable growth through responsible business practices, encouraging innovation and investment in sustainable industries, taking into account the specificities of areas such as consumption, culture, education, and production. Thus, sustainable development intertwined with innovation is a driving force for change in entrepreneurship, and the implementation of sustainable innovation is a tool in the transition to a sustainable society, although the consequences of management innovation can be complex, affecting various stakeholders.

The transition to sustainability can face a lot of challenges, like the actual impact of each company, or the difficulty of classifying the environmental impact of some activities, or the difficulty of predicting how economic agents will react to changing incentives (Mollenkamp, 2025). These difficulties require the joint efforts of science and business, government institutions and non-governmental organisations, as well as all stakeholders and

communities, because the relevance of the issues related to innovative entrepreneurship and sustainable development transcends the interests of individual groups and their resolution guarantees the present and the future.

Conclusion

Innovative entrepreneurship is a significant phenomenon in economic and social progress, and investment in the innovation sector stimulates long-term economic progress and sustainability. Data from European and global statistics confirm the importance of innovation—countries with a high level of innovative activity are also global economic leaders. But combining entrepreneurship with innovative activity not only leads to economic prosperity, it is also a prerequisite for sustainable development. To this must be added the fact that the rise of digital technologies creates new moral challenges, such as data privacy and cybersecurity. To address these moral challenges, companies must adopt a proactive approach that prioritizes ethical values and principles. (Kirov, 2023, pp. 39-40)

Therefore, innovation must be viewed as a complex process with enormous economic, social and moral. Therefore, innovation should be seen as a complex process with enormous economic and social impact, and focusing on the implementation of sustainable innovation predisposes entrepreneurship to overcoming environmental, social, and economic challenges in order to ensure the prosperity of present and future generations.

In order to achieve progress in innovative entrepreneurship, measures need to be taken to create favourable conditions for innovative activity and stimulate innovative receptivity in business, creating a stable business environment in which it will be ready to participate in high-risk innovative projects. Stimulating innovative activity plays a decisive role in the development of successful competitiveness, which in turn is a hallmark of sustainable development.

A comprehensive analysis of innovation and entrepreneurship would make it possible to determine their place in the country's sustainable development and economic security system, combining the three elements of economic success, social responsibility, and environmental balance—and combining them with the formation of an effective innovation system, improvement of educational potential, stimulation of demand for innovation, investment in infrastructure, etc.

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